

FCT RESEARCH AND INNOVATION LANDSCAPE COUNTRY PROFILE: UK

About ENACT

ENACT is a knowledge network focused on the fight against crime and terrorism (FCT). The network is funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme in Cluster 3 – Civil Security for Society. The project addresses the call topic HORIZON-CL3-2022-SSRI-01-02 ‘Knowledge Networks for Security Research & Innovation’, aiming to collect, aggregate, process, disseminate and make the most of the existing knowledge in the FCT area.

The project aims to satisfy two major ambitions,

- Provide evidence-based support to the decision-makers in the EU research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem in the FCT domain, targeted explicitly at enabling more effective and efficient programming of EU-funded R&I for the fight against crime and terrorism.
- Act as a catalyst for the uptake of innovation by enhancing the visibility and reliability of innovative FCT security solutions.

Report Feedback

We’re collecting feedback on this report through the EU Survey Platform, if you’d like to share your thoughts anonymously please click on the link below.

<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/enact-report-feedback>

**Funded by
the European Union**

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Copyright

This report contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Overview

The **Fight against Crime and Terrorism (FCT)** domain is a critical pillar within the European Union's security research framework, designed to address the increasingly complex and transnational threats facing Europe today. **FCT** research aims to provide innovative solutions, tools, and knowledge to empower law enforcement, policymakers, and civil society to prevent, detect, and respond to criminal and terrorist activities across the continent. The European Union supports collaborative research and innovation through key programmes like **Horizon Europe**, focusing on multidisciplinary approaches that combine advanced technology with robust legal, ethical, and societal safeguards.

In line with **ENACT**'s objectives, this flash report is part of a series of reports that reviews the **FCT R&I** ecosystem in different countries based on their participation in EU-funded **Security Research** under the **FCT** area between 2021 and 2024. The data used for the report comes from the most recent data available from **CORDIS** and the **Horizon Dashboard**, combined with data processed by **ENACT** under its **Structured Knowledge Base (SKB)**.

United Kingdom Infobox

Capital: London

Official EU Language(s): English

EU Member State:

1 January 1973 – 31 January 2020

Figures

- **Geographical size:** 242,945 km²
- **Population:** 69,281,400 (mid-2024 estimate)

Despite the **United Kingdom's** (UK) exit from the European Union and subsequent delay in full association with the Horizon Europe programme, the UK has retained a significant involvement within the European research and innovation landscape, demonstrating a commitment to the European research agenda and continued close cooperation in the area of security. Within Horizon Europe specifically, the UK has continued to be among the **top five countries** for signed grants and for overall participation by UK entities, demonstrating a strong commitment to the FCT research area in Europe.

Overall, the UK shows a diverse set of expertise across policy areas, with a large number of stakeholders contributing across the security sector. Increasing engagement from end-users, such as law enforcement agencies, also ensures a high consideration of operational needs and requirements, maximising opportunities for exploitation.

Country overview in FCT Research & Innovation

The UK's country profile in the **FCT** domain will be examined from three perspectives: policy coverage, functional coverage, and technology, in accordance with the **EU Civil Security Taxonomy (EUCST)**.

In 2025, ENACT developed a flash report¹ based on exhibitors at the Home Office Security and Policing Event.² As part of this exercise, ENACT catalogued more than 400 exhibitors, with the majority primarily based in the UK, and added them to the ENACT Stakeholder Map.³ Therefore, analyses in this report show a much higher number of stakeholders than in some other country reports that may only include participants from the Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe research programmes.

FCT Policy Coverage

For UK stakeholders, the policy coverage charts indicate comprehensive expertise across a range of topics aligned with the **Fight against Crime and Terrorism (FCT)** policy areas. In particular, based on the thematic areas of the **EUCST** for **FCT**, the UK shows an especially strong expertise in **Cybercrime**-related areas, alongside significant clusters of expertise across the broader spectrum of **FCT** challenges.

The following graph illustrates the policy coverage of the participants, categorised into the main **Security Research** areas: **OC (Organised Crime)**, **TR (Terrorism and Radicalisation)**, **CC (Cybercrime)**, and **HSI (other Horizontal Societal Issues)**.

Figure 1 - Policy coverage across UK participants in the ENACT Stakeholders Directory

While **Cybercrime** appears as the top domain, there are still an extensive number of organisations focused on tackling issues and challenges related to **Terrorism and Radicalisation**, **Organised Crime**, and **Horizontal and Societal Issues**.

¹Gibson, H., & Piotrowicz, C. (2025). ENACT Flash Report 06 - Home Office Security and Policing Event 2025 (1.0). European Network against Crime and Terrorism (ENACT)

²<https://www.securityandpolicing.co.uk/>

³<https://enact-eu.net/enact-fct-stakeholder-map/>

This demonstrates that UK entities are well-placed to provide knowledge and services to the European market, with an adaptability to a wide range of harms and threats.

Figure 2 illustrates where the UK appears to have clear pockets of noteworthy capabilities across each of the four policy areas. Under **Organised Crime**, there is strong alignment in areas related to **Trafficking in Human Beings, Trafficking of Goods** and **Cargo Crime**, perhaps necessitated by the UK’s geographic position as an island, which requires unique capabilities to monitor the legality of import and export processes.

Both the **Protection of Public Spaces** and **Radicalisation** also feature prominently, reflecting the UK’s recent and historic challenges related to terrorist attacks and radicalised individuals. Within **Cybercrime**, innovation and growth are particularly visible in areas related to **Darknets**, including **Cryptocurrencies, Encryption**, and **5G technologies**. Under **Horizontal and Societal Issues**, the UK appears to hold a strong position in **Community Policing**, an area closely associated with UK policing practices, alongside **Conventional Forensics**.

Overall, this distribution highlights a wide-ranging set of capabilities offered by UK organisations that could provide clear benefits to the broader European **FCT** landscape.

Figure 2 - Policy coverage at level 3 across UK stakeholders

FCT Functions Coverage

An analysis of the functions coverage for UK-based stakeholders demonstrates that the UK has a wide base of entities addressing almost all of the **FCT** functional areas. This highlights that UK entities can make a significant contribution across the **FCT R&I** area, and have a strong focus on ensuring that the products and services available are aligned to the needs of end-user organisations.

Specifically, the data highlights extensive capabilities that address **Data, Information & Intelligence Gathering, Management and Exploitation**, the **Detection of Goods, Substances, Assets, and People and Incidents**, and **Secure Public Communication, Data and Information Exchange**. Such areas are closely linked to operational needs and capabilities, complemented by a cluster of stakeholders who work in the area of **Training and Exercises**, highlighting the need for expertise across the whole deployment lifecycle.

Only the functional area of **Physical Access Control** has a significantly lower representation among UK stakeholders, while more niche areas, such as **Mobility and Deployability** and **Decontamination and Neutralisation**, are also less represented in the data. Further research as to whether a lack of funding, higher barriers to market entry, lack of end-user need, or other factors play a role in this distribution is required.

Overall, the UK offers a strong stakeholder base across **Data and Intelligence, Detection Methods**, and **Training**, covering many of the key areas of law enforcement activities. Furthermore, as this stakeholder base draws from beyond the **R&I** landscape and includes multiple organisations with commercial offerings, the UK appears to be in a strong place within the highly competitive security market.

Figure 3 - Functions coverage across UK stakeholders

FCT Technology Domain Coverage

The mapping of technological capabilities mirrors much of the aforementioned trends in the policy and functions areas. Digital capabilities continue to be some of the strongest offerings from UK stakeholders, with **Digital Forensics**, **Internet-based Investigation**, and **Data Analytics** occupying three of the top four spots in the technology coverage. The other spot relates to **General Equipment**, which highlights the ongoing need from end users to not only have access to the latest technologies but ensure they have access to the hardware and equipment to carry out their roles safely and effectively.

Overall, UK stakeholders offer excellent coverage across the full spectrum of technology areas from the **EUCST**. This positions UK stakeholders as well aligned to the needs and requirements of the UK **FCT** security market, highlighting the opportunities to engage with both the **R&I** ecosystem as well as offer products and services directly to the European market.

Figure 4 - Technology coverage across UK stakeholders

Overview of UK's Horizon Europe participation metrics

Figure 5 compares the UK participation in Horizon Europe FCT programmes with the average for the EU, based on several key performance indicators for the domain. This highlights the UK's overall strong engagement and contribution to a range of topics. It should be noted that the UK has only been formally associated to Horizon Europe for only one of the four years of the framework programme's operation. For the first three years, while UK entities could continue to participate, they did so as Associated Partners, meaning they did not receive funding from the EU and could not act as a coordinator of a project. Due to the uncertainty, during this period, it may have been more difficult for entities to participate or to attract new entrants to the programme from the UK.

United Kingdom	30	1.73	€ 150,850.96	€ 154,100.96	7	€ 412,750.00
	Signed Grants	Average Participation	Average Total Cost	Average EU Contribution	SME Participation	SME Net EU Contribution
EU	41	18.12	€ 4,310,115.27	€ 3,987,660.71	172	€ 44,114,024.00
	Signed Grants	Average Participation	Average Total Cost	Average EU Contribution	SME Participation	SME Net EU Contribution

Figure 5 - UK project participation metrics compared to EU

Nevertheless, the data shows that **UK entities were involved in over 75% of successful consortia**, with an average of 1.73 entities participating per project. Participation from UK-based SMEs was lower than in many comparable European countries, **accounting for less than 5% of all SMEs** participating in Europe. Uncertainty related to UK participation may have been a contributing factor, while the strong emphasis on Innovation Actions during the first two years of the Horizon Europe **FCT** calls⁴, funded at 70% for SMEs, may also have affected participation levels.

Despite these challenges, the UK still ranks **third in terms of signed grants** and **fourth in overall participations**.

⁴De Tommaso, M., Sorace, S., Rosal Santos, I. M., Perez de Leon-Huet, V., Puustinen, J., & Kosmatopoulos, A. (2025). State of Play Policy Report 02 (1.0). European Network against Crime and Terrorism (ENACT). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18732057>

Country Code	Country	Signed Grants	Total Participations by Country	Net EU Contribution
EL	Greece	34	90	€ 26,290,653.24
ES	Spain	34	87	€ 17,409,733.00
IT	Italy	25	65	€ 17,590,799.90
UK	United Kingdom	30	52	€ 4,525,528.75
DE	Germany	27	48	€ 13,558,133.33
FR	France	21	43	€ 10,163,819.63
BE	Belgium	23	39	€ 9,606,930.16
FI	Finland	22	29	€ 5,954,334.86
PT	Portugal	21	28	€ 4,924,522.00
NL	Netherlands	19	27	€ 8,513,248.75
PL	Poland	16	26	€ 5,898,789.00
CY	Cyprus	18	23	€ 5,723,581.25
RO	Romania	14	22	€ 2,733,978.00
MD	Moldova	18	20	€ 1,288,120.00
AT	Austria	12	16	€ 4,347,636.75
BG	Bulgaria	6	13	€ 2,241,263.14
CZ	Czechia	10	13	€ 2,061,742.25
LU	Luxembourg	10	11	€ 4,401,443.75
CH	Switzerland	8	11	€ 0.00
IE	Ireland	7	10	€ 3,456,761.80
SE	Sweden	10	10	€ 2,128,071.25
EE	Estonia	7	9	€ 1,177,348.75
SI	Slovenia	4	8	€ 1,201,050.00
IL	Israel	4	5	€ 1,761,025.00
RS	Serbia	4	5	€ 478,496.25
HU	Hungary	3	4	€ 1,731,153.75
HR	Croatia	2	3	€ 602,395.26
LT	Lithuania	2	3	€ 420,080.00
MT	Malta	3	3	€ 283,356.00
NO	Norway	3	3	€ 1,071,048.75
SK	Slovakia	1	3	€ 831,038.50
CA	Canada	2	2	€ 418,417.50
DK	Denmark	2	2	€ 107,375.00
XK	Kosovo *	2	2	€ 78,750.00
MK	North Macedonia	2	2	€ 67,226.25
TR	Türkiye	1	2	€ 160,432.50
AL	Albania	1	1	€ 48,750.00
BA	Bosnia and Herzegovina	1	1	€ 59,625.00
IS	Iceland	1	1	€ 42,430.00
UA	Ukraine	1	1	€ 135,000.00

Table 1 - Comparison of UK to other participating countries in Horizon Europe for signed grants, total projet participations and net EU contribution

Participants Summary

UK participation in **Horizon Europe FCT** projects is reflective of the structure of the UK's research and innovation ecosystem. As shown in Figure 6, the UK has a significantly **higher participation rate from Higher Education institutions** compared with the **EU** average, with these organisations accounting for more than half of all participants. This can partly be attributed to differences in the UK model, where there are fewer entities classified as **Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs)** working in the security sector than in other **EU Member States**.

Furthermore, the UK shows a growing involvement of **end users**, although participation remains below the EU average and is **primarily represented by Law Enforcement Agencies**. Encouraging greater participation from end users is particularly beneficial for UK entities, as it enables both academic and industrial organisations to identify additional exploitation pathways and develop clusters of excellence.

Overall, most organisations have participated in only one or two projects, with the exception of **Sheffield Hallam University**, through its **Centre of Excellence in Terrorism, Resilience, Intelligence and Organised Crime Research (CENTRIC)**, which demonstrates extensive collaboration across the **FCT** domain.

Figure 6 - Organisational types of UK participation compared to the EU average in Horizon Europe projects

When analysing individual participants by their type, the following overview highlights the current key organisations involved.

Top End Users

End User	Total Cost	Signed Grants	Total EU Contribution
Scottish Police Authority	€ 90,937.50	3	€ 90,937.50
Home Office	€ 393,970.00	3	€ 393,970.00
The Mayor's Office for Policing And Crime (MOPAC)	€ 56,250.00	2	€ 56,250.00
West Yorkshire Combined Authority	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
Durham Constabulary	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
Dorset Police and Crime Commissioner	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
Police Service of Northern Ireland	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
Grand Total	€ 541,158	12	€ 541,158

Top Research and Technology Organisations

Research and Technology Organisation	Total Cost	Signed Grants	Total EU Contribution
The Police Foundation	€ 290,525.00	1	€ 290,525.00
Grand Total	€ 290,525	1	€ 290,525

Top Industry

Industrial Organisation	Total Cost	Signed Grants	Total EU Contribution
Thridium Limited	€ 0.00	2	€ 0.00
Trilateral Research Ltd	€ 247,500.00	2	€ 247,500.00
TheLogically Ltd	€ 165,250.00	1	€ 262,750.00
BAE Systems Digital Intelligence Limited	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
Air and Space Evidence Ltd	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
Operational Solutions Limited	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
Grand Total	€ 412,750	8	€ 510,250

Top Academia

Higher Education	Total Cost	Signed Grants	EU Contribution
Sheffield Hallam University	€ 889,125.00	14	€ 889,125.00
University of Greenwich	€ 1,041,275.00	2	€ 1,041,275.00
The University of Sheffield	€ 0.00	2	€ 0.00
Nottingham Trent University	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
Glasgow Caledonian University	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
Bournemouth University	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
University of Warwick	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
University of the West of England Bristol	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
Aston University	€ 288,125.00	1	€ 288,125.00
Durham University	€ 129,877.50	1	€ 129,877.50
King's College London	€ 648,502.50	1	€ 648,502.50
University of Derby	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
University of Northumbria at Newcastle	€ 206,691.25	1	€ 206,691.25
University of Dundee	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
University of Glasgow	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
Grand Total	€ 3,203,596	30	€ 3,203,596

Horizon Europe FCT Proposals Summary

The proposal-to-project pipeline is also strong in the UK, reflected in the significant number of proposals involving UK entities. Just **over 55% of all proposals included at least one UK entity**, demonstrating UK involvement across the full range of **FCT** call topics.

The figure below presents a comparative overview of UK and EU performance in **Horizon Europe FCT** proposal activity, enabling a direct analysis of the UK's contribution and competitiveness.

United Kingdom	154	28	283	€ 100,509,310.50	18%
	Eligible Proposals	Retained Proposals	Eligible Applications	Eligible EU	Success Rate
EU	278	39	4458	€ 1,099,171,410.00	14%
	Eligible Proposals	Retained Proposals	Eligible Applications	Eligible EU	Success Rate

Figure 7 - Statistics for Horizon Europe proposal submission for UK compared to the EU overall

The UK also demonstrates strong performance in the conversion of eligible proposals into funded projects, with an **average success rate of 18%**, significantly above the **EU average of 14%**. This highlights the strong contribution that UK partners bring to consortia and their ability to support successful proposal outcomes.

The **eligible EU contribution at the proposal stage** also provides a clearer indication of the level of funding requested by UK participants, as this figure was not affected by the reassignment of UK partners to **Associated Partner status**, which occurred after submission. On average, UK participants account for **just under 10% of the eligible EU contribution in each proposal**, reflecting the knowledge, products, and services they contribute.

Overall, these findings present a positive picture of the UK's participation and its ability to maintain its role as a **strong and strategic actor** within the European security research landscape, even after Brexit.

Horizon Europe FCT Projects Summary

The number of projects with strong UK participation shows that it continues to perform well, with UK entities both clustered in some projects and more spread out across others.

Acronym	Project Title	Type	No.
2PS	2PS - Prevent & Protect Through Support	RIA	5
CLARUS	Building clarity and preventing bias in digital forensic examination, interorganisational communication and interaction	RIA	3
TENSOR	Reliable biomeTric tEchnologies to asSist Police authorities in cOmbating terrorism and oRganized crime	IA	3
OSPREY	Online Safety and Security for Protection of Public-Facing Professionals and Democratic Resilience	RIA	3
SALVUS	SALVUS (Ensuring SAfer justice outcomes in onLine, including undercoVer, child sexUal abuse inveStigations)	RIA	3
ECLIPSE	PrEventing and Combating onLine and offline hate speech and dIsinformation through multidisciplinary innovation, education, and awareNeSs in Europe	IA	3
DETECTOR	Deepfake Evidence and Technology for Forensic Content Oversight and Research	RIA	3
ARIEN	ARTificial IntelligencE in fighting illicit drugs production and traffickiNg	IA	2
KOBAN	Identifying future capabilities for Community Policing	RIA	2
POLIICE	Powerful Lawful Interception, Investigation, and Intelligence	RIA	2
TENACITY	Travelling Intelligence Against Crime and Terrorism	IA	2
VIGILANT	Vital IntelligencE to Investigate ILlegal DisinformaTion	IA	2
BTL-COP	Building Trust and Leadership to challenge glocal aporophobic crime in a police Community Of Practice (BTL-COP)	RIA	2
GANNDALF	A Ground-breAking collaboratioN framework realizing the next era of cybercrime Detection And muLti-stakeholder investigation For LEAs, judicial ecosystems, and citizens.	RIA	1
ARMADILLO	Accurate Reliable Portable and Rapid Methods And Technologies for Detection of GHB Substances and Prevention Against Different Forms of VioLence and AssauLt SuppOrted by These Drugs	IA	1
VANGUARD	adVANced technoloGical solutions coupled with societal-oriented Understanding and AwaReness for Disrupting trafficking in human beings	IA	1
GATHERINGS	COMMON STANDARDS FOR SECURITY, PRIVACY AND COST OF THE SURVEILLANCE OF PUBLIC GATHERINGS	CSA	1
ENSEMBLE	ENhanced AI-baSEd cybercriMe-oriented collaBorative investigation technologies and capabiLitiEs	RIA	1
EMERITUS	Environmental crimes' intelligence and investigation protocol based on multiple data sources	IA	1

Acronym	Project Title	Type	No.
FALCON	Fight Against Large-scale Corruption and Organised Crime Networks	IA	1
GEMS	Gaming Ecosystem as a Multilayered Security Threat	RIA	1
IAMI	Identity Attributes Matrix Initiative	RIA	1
ISED	Innovative Solutions to Eliminate Domestic Abuse	IA	1
LAGO	LESSEN DATA ACCESS AND GOVERNANCE OBSTACLES	IA	1
PRESERVE	Ethical and Privacy-preserving Big Data platform for Supporting criminal investigations	RIA	1
PERIVALLON	Protecting the EuRopean territory from organised enVironmentAl crime through inteLLigent threat detectiON tools	IA	1
SAFE-CITIES	riSk-based Approach For the protEction of public spaces in European CITIES	IA	1
ForMAT	FORENSIC METHYLATION ANALYSIS TOOLSETS (FORMAT)	RIA	1
SALUS	Strengthening law enforcement with advanced IoT forensic tools and enriched investigation schemes, realised by a Software Defined Network Security-as-a-Service architecture	RIA	1

This level of engagement demonstrates the UK’s growing appetite to strengthen its engagement with the European **R&I** ecosystem, particularly following its full association with the **Horizon Europe Framework Programme**.

The following section presents a series of charts detailing the policy, functional, and technological coverage of projects involving UK participation, based on the comprehensive list of projects outlined above.

Figure 8 - Policy Project Coverage according to projects with UK participation

Figure 9 - L3 Policy Coverage according to projects with UK participation

Figure 10 - Functions coverage according to projects with UK participation

Figure 11 - Technology coverage according to projects with UK participation

Final Remarks

The UK continues to play a major role in European security research, with a growing momentum following its full association with the **Horizon Europe Framework Programme**. It still occupies a high position in the number of participations in **FCT** projects, albeit with limited coordination capacity in recent years.

Within the broader UK innovation ecosystem, the UK is represented by organisations with a strong set of capabilities across the board, addressing all four policy areas in Europe, with a particular focus on **Cybercrime**. Actual participations in **Horizon Europe** projects are almost equal across each of the policy areas; when combined with the stakeholder positioning, this demonstrates further opportunities for the UK to embed its expertise in **Cybercrime** into the European **R&I** space. Furthermore, UK participation is dominated by **Higher Education institutions**, which were perhaps shielded from the uncertainty created by Brexit, highlighting the value of the scientific excellence provided by UK institutions. Now, with full association, there are even greater prospects for UK entities, particularly those from **Industry** and **SMEs**, to engage with the programme.

Delving deeper into the gap between UK stakeholder expertise and current **Horizon Europe** participation, there is already strong involvement in projects relating to **Economic Crime, Corruption and Fraud, CBRN Threats, Child Sexual Abuse, and Darknets**. Comparing this to stakeholder capabilities, where the UK exhibits compelling capacity in **Cargo Crime, Protection of Public Spaces, Radicalisation, and Encryption and 5G Technologies**, there is a clear opportunity for consortia building projects in these spaces to take advantage of UK expertise.

In relation to the functional areas, there are three key areas of expertise represented within the stakeholders' data: **Data, Information & Intelligence Gathering, Management and Exploitation, Training and Exercises, and Detection of Goods, Substances, Assets, People and Incidents**. While these areas are primarily well aligned with current UK participation in **FCT** projects, there is a higher representation of UK organisations participating in projects relating to **Investigation and Forensics**. This demonstrates that those organisations participating in those projects must offer significant value and expertise to those consortia, and there is potential for the UK to capitalise on such involvement.

Considering the technology dimensions, the stakeholders' data shows that UK organisations have a clear cluster of experience relating to **Digital Forensics, Internet-based Investigation, and Data Analytics**. These areas of expertise can be applied across multiple policy domains and are also well aligned to current participations of UK organisations in **FCT** projects, thus highlighting that the UK is bringing some of its core areas of innovation into the European arena.

Overall, the UK continues to perform above expectations compared to the **EU** average success rate for applications, leading to high participation rates across the **FCT** programme. This reinforces the UK's position as a highly valued partner bringing significant expertise into the European **FCT R&I** ecosystem. Furthermore, the increasing engagement from **Law Enforcement Agencies** offers further opportunities for exchange of knowledge and expertise between the UK and Europe within the **FCT** domain.

For more information and guidance regarding the UK participation in the **CL3 Civil Society for Security Programme** and possible collaboration opportunities, please visit the **National Contact Points Portal**: <https://horizoneuropencpportal.eu/> and search for the **NCPs** from the UK.

A note on data sources

The data used to compile this report is from the following sources

- **ENACT Stakeholder Directory**, where relevant organisations participating in **Horizon Europe**, **Horizon 2020** or relevant security events have been compiled and categorised according to the **EU Civil Security Market Taxonomy** for policy levels two and three, functions and technology.
- **ENACT Project Directory**, where relevant projects have been compiled and categorised according to the **EU Civil Security Market Taxonomy** for policy levels two and three, functions and technology.
- The **Horizon Dashboard** for R&I Projects and R&I Proposals.⁵

An explorable version of the **ENACT Stakeholders Directory** is available on the **ENACT** website.⁶

⁵Horizon Dashboard - <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-dashboard>

⁶ENACT Stakeholders Map - <https://enact-eu.net/enact-fct-stakeholder-map/>

ENACT.

European Network Against
Crime and Terrorism

[@enact-network](https://www.linkedin.com/company/enact-network)

enact-eu.net

Scan the QR code to visit ENACT online
and read this report in digital format.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

